

RAIN WATER HARVESTING FOR RESIDENTIAL PROJECT DAULAT HEIGHTS IN SASWAD

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ABSTRACT:

Water scarcity is becoming the biggest problem in front of the world now. Many developing and developed countries few areas are affected by water scarcity. Many researchers have already made a point saying the biggest problem of is excessive exploitation of ground water and surface water resources deterioration. Few water resources used conventionally are river and reservoirs and are not sufficient to feed the water demand the major reason behind this is unbalance rainfall. Worldwide, rainwater harvesting systems are considered as a new water source. The main of this paper is to make efficient use of rainwater and adoption of newly launched concept of nature conversion. The system is actually built in saswad city, Maharashtra state of India. The cost of total project is Rs. 48060 and it can harvest 129600 liters of water.

KEY WORDS: Roof top, rain water harvesting, water scarcity. Catchment, Recharge pit

INTRODUCTION

Various communities around the world are going through the problem of water shortage, water table levels are dropping at a higher rate. The main reason behind dropping of water table is pumping of water table and hence droughts are more frequent. Researchers have found a solution to deal with this problem which can be adopted by everyone right from small residence, to big industries etc. The rain water harvesting is proven as one of the most prominent solution to deal with water scarcity. In this paper situation related to certain region of India is exploited, but all this concepts are truly applicable all parts of the world. In rainwater harvesting technique rain water is not allowed to flow through the land but it is stopped and stored for future use. The major success point is not how much rain fall but how much harvesting done.

Fig.1. Simple rain water harvesting system

Rainwater harvesting technique three process water collection, convey and storing the water for later use on clean surfaces may be roof or rock catchment. Rainwater harvesting is most commonly adopted technique now a day's either the water can be stored for later use or it can also be used for recharging ground water depending upon situation. Harvested rain water is clean soft and of high quality and helps in reducing dependence on ground water extracted from bore or from well.

ADVNTAGES OF RAIN WATER HARVESTING:

1. Easy to maintain: Utilization of rainwater harvesting systems provided great advantages to the society. Firstly, harvested rainwater can be a better uses of energy resource. Systems employed for collection of rain water are easy to use and understand very little maintenance is required.
2. Reduction in water bills: Collected water in rain harvesting system can be directly for various purposes e.g. irrigation purpose. For household and various small and large industries will reduce their utility bill.
3. Reduction in ground water demand: As population has arose the demand for water is also risen three fold. To feed this excess demand ground water is extracted. This may led to reduction in level of ground water may be in

few areas e.g. Latur in Maharashtra and it may face huge water scarcity.

4. Reduction in floods and soil erosion: In rainy season rain water collected in huge tanks which may help in avoiding flooding of water in low lying areas. The harvested rain water also helps in soil erosion and contamination of water with fertilizers and pesticides.

DISADVANTAGES OF RAIN WATER HARVESTING:

1. Unpredictable rainfall: It is very hard task to predict the rain fall. In literature advice is been made to not only to depend upon rain water harvesting projects as a sole source of water. Many authors in literature have suggested to used rain water where rainfall with higher rate.

2. Initial high cost: The size and technology used may affect the cost of rain water harvesting project. The major problem with this kind of project is water cannot be derived directly like in case of solar panels.

3. Regular maintenance: Regular maintenance is needed for harvesting tank and water otherwise water will become home for many animals like mosquitoes, insects and lizards.

4. Storage limits: The storage and collection facilities may also impose an restriction on how much rainfall can be stored and reuse. During heavy raining the collection systems may not hold all rainwater which may end up going to rivers.

COMPONENTS OF RAIN WATER HARVESTING SYSTEM:

A Rainwater harvesting system comprises of components for – transporting rainwater through water pipes or drains, filtration, and tanks for storage of harvested water.

The list of components required for rain water harvesting

1. The roof
2. Gutters
3. Gutter Ground
4. Down sprouts
5. Debris type
6. Final sediment filtration
7. First flush diverter
8. Surge/pump tank
9. Water storage
10. Water Disinfection

Fig. 2. Rainwater Harvesting system schematic

The design of RWH consists of following

1. Rainwater Catchment and Conveyance
2. Rainwater Storage and Tank Sizing and
3. Rainwater Quality and Treatment

With above literature it is found that the rainwater harvesting system can be developed with qualitative and quantitative approach for the case study under consideration. This paper mainly aims to explore the economic benefit of rainwater harvesting system and the methodology has been demonstrated through application to Residential Project “DAULAT HEIGHTS”.

STUDY AREA:

The Project is located at Saswad near Pune. Satellite image of the same is shown below.

Fig.3. Satellite Image of Daulat Height

PROBLEM FORMULATION:

- Design of rainwater harvesting system using satellite image of the project.
- For this taking catchment area of Open space in front of A building & behind B building including entry and exit roads & terraces of both buildings.
- Calculate area by using sanctioned plan.
- The slope of the catchment shall be checked by Dumpy level.
- Analyze the potential of runoff from the rainfall from the catchment and suggest suitable recharge pit locations and also volume of rainwater to be recharge in the ground.
- What will be the approximate expenditure for these recharge pits.
- If we want to construct underground storage tank, what will be the approximate expenditure.

DESIGN OF RWH SYSTEM:

In this paper design of RWH System for the proposed location at Daulat Heights, by visual inspection & available plans is presented.

FOR CATCHMENT 1: (Calculations are for 1 storm, considering intensity of storm as 2cm/hr)

Collected data -

1. Catchment area
 1. Rooftop area = 1114 m²
 2. Open area = 1296 m²
 3. Road Area = 1664 m²

Assume,

2. Average rainfall intensity = 4 cm per 2 hr.
3. Runoff coefficient,
 - For roof top area = 0.95
 - For open area = 0.8
4. Storm duration = 2 hr.

By using rational formulae's

For Roof Top Area

$$Q = C \times I \times A / 3.6$$

$$Q = 0.95 \times 20 \times 1114 \times 10^{-6/3.6}$$

$$Q = 5.879 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$$

For Open Area

$$Q = C \times I \times A / 3.6$$

$$Q = 0.8 \times 20 \times 2960 \times 10^{-6/3.6}$$

$$Q = 0.013 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$$

$$\text{Thus, Total runoff} = 5.879 \times 10^{-3} + 0.013 \\ = 0.018 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$$

DESIGN OF RECHARGE PIT:

The recharge pit should be filled with the metal, to recharge silt free water. Hence the materials to be filled in the pit are 60 mm metal, 40 mm metal, 20 mm metal, fine sand. The material should be filled depth wise in the pit. The coarser material to be filled at the bottom and finest on the top. The uppermost fine sand layer can be separated from the 20 mm metal layer by using non corrosive wire mesh. It will help for the yearly maintenance.

DEPTH OF MATERIAL FOR RECHARGE PITS:

Material to be filled	% depth of material	Depth (in m)
60 mm metal	30	0.3
40 mm metal	30	0.3
20 mm metal	20	0.2
Fine Sand	20	0.2

ESTIMATION AND COSTING OF RECHARGE PITS:

No.	Item	Quantity	Rate	Amount
1	Excavation	9 (cum)	140/- per cum	1260/-
2	Labour	4 (numbers)	500/- per day	2000/-
3	Material	9 cft	1200/- per cum	10,800/-
			TOTAL =	14060/-

Cost of Storage Tank for 5000lit = 13000/-

Cost of Pipe = 170m x 100/- = 17000/-

Cost of Motor = 4000/-

Total cost of RWH system = 48060/-

CONCLUSION:

Recharging of ground water is gradual process; it's not possible to increase the water table immediately after constructing recharge structures even after constructing best recharge structure available in the world it needs some time to acquire recharge. Developed recharge points helps in increasing or rejuvenating water table. And it immediately starts converting rain water which used to drain for many centuries. Author in this paper developed a working system at construction site named Daulat Heights in Pune, Maharashtra. The project has storing capacity of 129600 liters of water with just Rs. 48060/-.

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